

Training Material For MAMMOth created by the RUG

Traveling Exhibit: Digital Dilemmas

Purpose: supporting AI literacy development

Audience: general public

Medium: exhibit

Duration: ~30 minutes

Support level: individually explorable

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Short Description: 'Digital Dilemmas: AI and the Invisible Biases' is a traveling exhibit, designed to raise awareness, inform individuals about the pervasive nature of AI (bias) and invite people to share their opinion on the matter. By showcasing real-world examples of AI applications and related errors, it provides an introduction to AI functions, including its inherent biases. The exhibition features engaging elements designed to encourage active participation and provoke thoughtful discussions: a series of posters and a mini-podcast educate the public, while a physical neural net and a bulletin board give space for interactivity, reflection and discussion.

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Notes:

- A supplementary handbook is available for this material
- Component 2 is not available in English